

STATE OF WATER RESOURCES IN NAVAI REGION

Shodiev Sanjar Ruzikulovich

Professor of Navoi State University

Ruziyev Jahongir Abdumumin og'li

Teacher of Navoi State University

Nabiyeva Parvina Jamshid kizi

Master of Navoi State University

Abstract: Navoi region is considered the driest region of Uzbekistan and most of it is made up of desert zones. Therefore, the annual rainfall does not exceed 120-180 mm. The uneven distribution of water resources creates additional difficulties for the population. Water is one of the main factors for the sustainable functioning of agriculture and industry in particular.

Keywords: artificial reservoir, river, evaporation, water scarcity, water pollution, ditch, groundwater.

Today, there is no place left untouched by man, the poles have been discovered, the continents have been discovered, and even small islands have been reached by man. Although this is a positive result in itself, it is not without its negative aspects. Over the past 10 years, the anthropogenic factor has caused great harm to nature. River waters, atmospheric air, forests, and even soil, mountain glaciers, fauna and flora have been greatly damaged. As the ozone hole has grown, the annual temperature on the earth's surface has increased by 3-4 degrees. As a result, a number of negative consequences have appeared, such as the problem of water shortage, salinization, and desertification. Similar problems are not absent in our country. Especially since a large part of the Navoi region is made up of the Kyzylkum desert, the evaporation process is several times greater than the annual precipitation. Navoi region is one of the regions with the lowest precipitation in the republic. The main reason for this is that the region has an arid and semi-arid climate. Therefore, the issues of rational use, protection and redistribution of water resources are of strategic importance for the socio-economic development of the region.

The water resources of Navoi region mainly rely on the following sources:

The Zarafshan River is the main surface water of the region. The river flow is greatly reduced before it enters the region, as a large amount of water is taken for irrigation in the upper reaches.

Large and small reservoirs:

-Tudakol Reservoir

-Karakol Reservoir

-Eski Angor and other reservoirs are among them. These reservoirs are mainly used for irrigation, industry, livestock breeding, and domestic needs.

Groundwater - There are artesian water reserves in the Nurota mountain range and Kyzylkum regions, the quality of which is relatively stable, but the reserves are limited.

Water use in Navoi region mainly falls into the following areas:

More than 80% of agriculture - cotton, grain, viticulture, and melon crops - is heavily dependent on irrigation. In addition, the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine, chemical and energy enterprises are major consumers of water. Most importantly, the supply of drinking water for the population is unstable.

Improper use of water resources in the region leads to several negative consequences, including salinization of irrigated lands, increased turbidity in rivers and canals, increased biogenic substances in reservoirs, and degradation of ecosystems.

In recent years, a number of measures have been implemented to manage water resources. Water-saving technologies (drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation) are being introduced.

Reconstruction work is underway at Tudakol and other reservoirs. An integrated management system with neighboring regions is being established in the Zarafshan River basin. Standards for reducing water consumption in agriculture have been tightened.

In recent years, the number of urbanized areas in Navoi region has increased. One of the main reasons for this is the increase in population. At the same time, in centralized areas, conditions are very favorable.

The planned level of drinking water coverage in the region is 84.9%. The volume of water resources used in the country is 51-53 billion m³ per year. In water distribution: agriculture -90-91%, the municipal sector - 4.5%, and industry - about 1.4%. These indicators indicate that water resources are under great pressure in regions such as Navoi, which mainly need agriculture, industry and drinking water. In particular, the mineralization (salinity) of river water in the region is high, so groundwater is often unsuitable for drinking water.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the water resources of Navoi region are under constant pressure due to the arid climate, limited natural resources and

industrial development. Although the demand for water is increasing every year, the existing reserves do not fully meet this need. Therefore, the widespread introduction of water-saving technologies, modernization of reservoirs, scientifically based use of groundwater and integrated management of the Zarafshan River flow are the main ways to ensure the ecological stability of the region.

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